

Accounting Profitability and Future Share Prices: Evidence from Investment Sector of Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 07, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 19, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Profitability Ratios, Future Share Price, Pakistan Stock Exchange</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5224204</p>	<p><i>Financial ratios is a key attribute of valuable accounting information. Profitability ratios enables investors in yielding investments. This paper investigates the effect of profitability ratios of investment and securities firm on their future shares prices for a period of (2009-2018) listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange. The independent variables are, Return on Assets, Return on equity, Earning per Share, Price Earnings Ratio and FSP (future share price) were used as dependent variables. Twenty one firms' data were available for the said variables and were used for estimations. The current accounting profitability ratio, price earnings ratio has positively significant relationship with future share price, while earnings per share, return on asset, and return on shareholder equity insignificant to the future share prices of investment firms. It shows that the future share prices of investment and securities firms can only be predicted with the help of current price earnings ratio in Pakistan.</i></p>

Introduction

The aim of this study is to examine the association between profitability ratios and future share price of the investment firms listed on Pakistan stock exchange (PSX). Financing and investment are two important decision firms' takes to increase shareholder values. Firms used various modes of financing, among, one is issuing of equity shares (Alagidede and Panagiotidis, 2010). Firm used mix of debt and equity, any one of means used alone yields to lower costs more returns. Depend on financial needs firm increases issuing of shares to finance its projects (Eita, 2012). Investor needs authentic information and better understanding of the external and internal environment in the stock exchange before investing in the stocks. It is needful for investors to take the right decision in the stock market for generating profit and reducing risk. Financial ratios are helpful to analyzed and predict stock prices. The most important ratios are liquidity ratios, profitability ratios, solvency ratios, efficiency ratios and investments ratio which are used to identify the associated risks and performance of a firm in equity markets (Lui & O'Farrell, 2009). In this study we only used profitability ratios, based on accounting information firms performance are assess in terms of its earnings generated from its operations. Higher profitability ratios indicate better financial performance but several studies have identified that non accounting information like speculation, gambling, and forced sales also influences the future share price (Francis & Schipper, 1999; Cheng, Shamsher & Annuar, 2008; Ullah *et al* 2021). According to King & Langli (1998) substantial differences exists between accounting data and share price, across time variation and among countries. Oyerinde (2009), Umar & Musa, (2013) have suggests evidence empirically on the relationship between price of stock-movement and accounting statements. An analysis regarding which factors directly affected stock price and to what extent, the valuation help an investor to design and make the better investment decision in a firm and in the financial market. According to the study of Callen, Khan and Lu, (2013) poor quality of accounting information has likely connected with high future share returns through vulnerability about stock valuation parameter and with delayed price change, high future share returns also ideal for stock value disclosure.

The positive impact studies of profitability ratios used to examine returns of a firm are ROA (return on asset), ROE (return on shareholders' equity), EPS (Earning per share) and PER (Price earnings ratio) to predict stock price variations (Campell and Shiller 1988; Lewellen 2004; Dzikevicius and Saranda 2011; Agrman and Yilmaz, 2018; Khan *et al* 2013). These ratios are derived from accounting information provide in the annual financial statement of the company's Future share price fluctuation based on a number of external and internal factors or both. Like earnings of the firm, demand and supply of the shares in thee. Different scholar's uses return on assets to measure the financial returns of the firms. Profitability of owner's investments is measured and calculated through return on shareholder's equity. Earnings per share are the business profits of a share, attributable to every common share. The EPS have the strong effect on future share prices over the longer period as the earnings grows than share price of company generally increases and decreases when company returns decline, but not in shorter period. Price earnings ratio showings the dollar sum that an investor need to put

resources into an organization in for accepting one dollar of that organization's earnings later on. The investigation dissected the effect of accounting profitability proportions on the future share price of the investment sector in Pakistan.

Arising studies has clarified statistical relationship financial earnings and stock returns in future (Novy-Marx, 2013). Shen and Stark (2013) checked whether accounting based valuation models have in-example illustrative force as well as can conceivably be utilized as a device of budget report estimation in creating helpful appraisals. As per their discoveries, a valuation model particular utilizing an all-inclusive model which incorporates book value, income, innovative costs, capital consumptions, profits, capital commitments, and other information assessed for high-and low-intangible assets firms independently utilizing value an incentive as the deflator, is by all accounts a sensible by and large methodology. That stock split supply financial investors with information about the possibility of significant development in future returns. Normally the firms that lead stock split experience expanding stock return in the wake of doing the stock split.

The paper is organized by section one discusses the introduction, section two present the literature review, section three explain the data and methodology, section four presents the results and discussion and section five conclude the paper with policy recommendations for investors. Fama and French (2015) expanded the model CAPM, adding accounting information and all the more explicitly adding two accounting factors: investment and returns. Fama and French (2018) guaranteed that their five-factor resource evaluating model, intended to predict pattern in returns because of risks related with returns, is invalid and this model sensitive to the choose of the returns. Barillas and Shanken (2018) identified that the new model derived by Hou et al., (2017) and Fama and French (2018) are profoundly significant for identifying values and earnings factors in investigating stated anomalies but yet a few issues uncertain.

2.0 Literature Review

In an effective market, the share cost isn't anticipated effectively and the market separated into three degrees of effectiveness, for example (1) weak form market, (2) semi-strong market, (3) strong form market (Malkiel and Fama, 1970). In a weak form market, the present share cost completely reflects past information. In a semi-strong form, the present share cost of stock reflects full information, for example, profit, profits, and the executives' exercises. While in a strong form market, the share cost additionally reflects inner information since market cost has just mirrored that information. Lau, Lee, and McNish (2002) examined 82 firms listed in Singapore stock exchange had showings insignificant relationship between the BV and PER with SP. Similarly 163 Malaysian firms had showings positive significant relationship between the PER and SP during 1988-96. According to Fisher and Statman (2000) investigation the relationship between PER and future market returns are not good indicator in short run, but better in forecasting stock returns in the long run. Refinancing has no effect on outer financing and it's connected negatively with future share return but most relevant with assertive accounting and over-speculation (Richardson & Sloan, 2003). From Johannesburg stock exchange (JSE), researchers, identified the relationship between PER and SP during 1990 to 2000, and found there is no significant relationship between the PER and SP (Auret and Sinclair, 2006; Khan *et al* 2013). Dimitropoulos & Asteriou (2009) found Return on Assets significantly positively influence the stock price of 101 non-financial registered firm on Athens stock exchange for a period of (1995-04). Durre and Giot (2007) examined the stock price movements in the USA and UK by using co-integration framework and found a long-run relationship among returns, yields on longer-term government Bond and future share price for 13 countries for period (1973-04). Further they identified that long-term movement mostly derived by the earnings, while yields on longer-term government Bond have impact on shorter-term. According to Huang (2009) the standard-deviation SD of income, measure by book value to a company's income instability and identify its negative relationship for future stock return. Mirfakhr et al., (2011) examined the effect of financial variables on share prices in Tehran Stock Exchange from 1998-07; they found that EPS is significantly positive while PER significantly negatively related to the stock price in Tehran equity market. Bhatt and Sumangala (2012) examined the effect of EPS on MV of equity share of the 50 companies and found that EPS significantly affect equity share. Nguyen (2014) studied the relationship between share prices and accounting information with same model used by Ohlson (1995) for 430 registered firm on Vietnam stock exchange in 2009, their main finding suggests, BV, EPS, ROE, debts had positively significant influence on share price. Analysts locate that in arising and created market firm with more profit have significantly high future share returns than lower income firm (Novy-Marx, 2013). According to the study of Jatoi et al., (2014) the cement sector firm, the earning per share has significantly related with market-value of share in Pakistan stock exchange (PSX). Laing & Dunbar (2015) had empirically evaluated the performance measures EVA, EPS, ROA and ROE against the shares prices in the four major Australian banks for a period of 2003-11, they found EPS had significantly positively related but others insignificantly related to the share price. Some researchers have distinguished and analyzed the connection among a company's returns and future stock returns.

Subing, Kusumah, & Gusni (2017) had analyzed different factors relationship for 18 companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange with future share price during 2008-15, their panel data regression findings indicated that the price earnings ratios, return on assets and oil prices have a positive relationship with company stock

prices, while inflation has a negative impact on company stock prices. Kumar, (2017) Investigate the relationship between PER and share price for 8 firms for a period of 2011-16, and found very strongly significant association between PER to the share price. The empirical analysis of Jiang, Qi and Tang (2018) noticed critical and cross-sectional positively predication for future shares return in the Chinese financial stock exchange. Bratamanggala (2018) conducted a case study and research a company of the LQ45 in Indonesian Stock Exchange during 2012-16. The finding indicates that the. Found that EPS, Price to BV and Return on Assets has significant impact on stock prices. Hung (2018) had investigate the relationship between financial information on share prices of the 273 large firms from the Vietnam Stock Exchange during 2006-16 by using the multiple regressions and have found that, EPS, book value, cash flow from operating activities and firm size have positive relationships with future share price. Edem, Ekwe & Azubike (2018) analyzed the association among financial ratios and share price by ex-post-facto research design during 2009-15, the researcher found that EPS have a significant positive links with future share price by suggesting that financial analysts and prospective investors should rely more on EPS and cash deposit in predicting the future share price fluctuation. According to the investigation of Rosyid (2018) the impact of capital ratio as CAR indicator, liquidity as LDR and profitability as Return on Equity (ROE) together has significant relationship with the Share Price of PT Bank Indonesia. By using analytical techniques in multiple linear-regression, research identified simultaneously significant impact of CAR, LDR and ROE on share price, while partially ROE in significant to the share price. Nautiyal & Kavidayal (2018) identified the effect of institutional variables on firm's stock price of NIFTY 50 Index, by collecting data from 30 actively traded companies during 1995–14. They found that higher debts insignificantly related to the future share price. Further, EPS identified weak relationship with the share price variation, which assists investors and analysts to assess the stocks of various groups for investments. The above literature validates the relationship among financial rations and future share of listed prices in the developing and developed world. Very few studies has been carried to check the impact of profitability ratios on future share prices in Pakistan, it has concluded that all the explanatory variables has potential effect on the explained variable. The main variables will be estimated to understand it true impact, each is discussed followed by the relevant hypothesis. Return on asset, capital ratio and debt to equity ratio has insignificant to the share prices returns, while beta and price earnings ratio has significantly and positively and significantly affecting the share prices return of banks (Afrino and Masdupi, 2019).

Yin, Wei and Han (2020) study identify that firm with more returns; instability has generously reduced the predicated stock return than other with low return. Nurdin & Abdani (2020) study that acquiring per share return and degree of profitability significantly affects stock return yet stock split is likewise found significantly affects stock return. The aftereffect of this investigation demonstrates that firms that have higher returns will give high stock returns to investors. In addition, firms that lead stock parts get higher stock returns than organizations that are not in Indonesia stock exchange. Earnings per share (EPS) have significantly and negatively, while return on shareholder equity (ROE) a significantly and positively effects on share prices of food and beverage companies in Indonesia stock exchange (Lusiana, 2020).

F&B firms' financial return has been influenced by the financial crisis but, their book value and market value doesn't appear to be fundamentally influenced in the Athens Stock Exchange (Panagiotakopoulou et al, 2020). According to analysis of Azimli (2020) just beta and book-to-market impacts are huge and added stock returns and venture factors improve neither the pricing nor the financial performance, can't explain to profits and neglect to clarify regular stocks' pricing behaviour in a developing business market. Most valuation models are utilizing either accounting variables (income, book values, flow of incomes to innovation costs) or financial market information (like beta, market value, premium or interest). The higher the correlation between these factors the better the explanatory power of the model (Belesis, Sorros and Karagiorgos, 2020). A time series results depicts that gross profits anomaly exists and higher earnings yields in the PSX and asset pricing model can be used to predicts stocks prices (Tharwani, Chhapra, Shakeel & Sarwat 2020).

Stock prices had positively connected with profitability and higher returns can't reduce the debts policy. Higher returns significantly increased the dividend and increasing dividend policy has increased the share returns. Dividend policy and Debt and have no mediating effect on return on equity on the shares earnings (Akhmadi, Nurohman & Robiyanto, 2020). A taxable income has positively connecting and suggesting additional information about income and future share returns but no signal about forecasted errors (Blaylock, Lawson, & Mayberry, 2020). According to Hertina et al., (2020) price earnings ratio, debt to equity ratio and return on assets, and have a significantly impact on share prices return of the Indonesia stock exchange listed firms (property and real estate sector).

As indicated by Mohamed et al; (2021) in the four indicators return on shareholders' equity, return on assets and EPS, the return margin on shareholders wealth is the main indicator and return on assets is the least. EPS is the most persuasive measure and revenue margin the least in Abu Dhabi securities exchange and the Dubai financial market. The lockdown arrangements, both in-country and around the world, drove bigger decreases in public stock price contingent on pandemic seriousness, work environment versatility, and pay backing obligation strategies. The size of the worldwide securities exchange crash in response to the pandemic is commonly bigger

than a standard resource model asset pricing model suggests (Davis, Liu and Sheng, 2021). A positive consistency analyzed for some stock as undervalued, overvalued and fairly valued in relation to its stock opening prices while some are inconsistent to price earnings ratio (Nordin, Rahim, & Adnan, 2021). According to Kurniawan, (2021) the outcomes indicated that partially return on Assets and debt to equity has no bigger impact on shares earnings but asset turnover has a positive connection. As study of Pandey (2021) has identified that prior day's exchanging prices, prior week's exchanging prices, and prior year's exchanging prices have related with current share prices. The study of Nadyayani & Suarjaya (2021) indicated that ROE, NPM and ROA, has significantly and positively links to future share earnings. NPM and ROA partially has a significant positive effect on stock returns while ROE has a positively but insignificantly related to the share earnings. According to Khazaei, Karimi & Mozaffari, (2021) optimization predicted that stock portfolio algorithm created by MOPSO has a better results compared to the algorithms used for four risk criteria except conditional risk analysis through the stock price predicting model with meta-innovative procedure in pharmaceuticals firms. A positive hedge return predicated that a risk-averse investor demand in extra earnings to hold shares for high equity risk-returns, and willing to pay high prices for shares with worthwhile hedging beta (Dunbar, 2021). As indicated by Narayan, Phan and Liu, (2021) the time series information indicated that lockdowns, bans on travel, and monetary bundles all positively affected the G7 securities exchanges earnings in COVID-19, however lockdowns were best in decreasing its impacts.

2.1 Hypothesis Development

- H1: Current year returns on assets (year, t) are significantly positively associated with their future share price (year, t + 1) of investment firms.
- H2: Current year returns on equity (year, t) are significantly positively related with their future share price (year, t+1) of investment firms.
- H3: Current year earnings per share (year, t) are significantly positively associated with their future share price (year, t + 1) of investment firms.
- H4: Current year price earnings ratio (year, t) are significantly positively associated with their future share price (year, t+1) of investment firms.

Conceptual Framework

3.0 Research Methodology

Firms included in this study are investment banks, speculation and securities firm listed in Pakistan stock exchange. Those firms were included whose data were available from 2009-2018.

Table 1: Variables Measurements

Variables	Description
Dependent Variable:	
Future Share Price	Current market price
Independent Variables:	
Returns on Asset	Return on Assets is measure by Net income after Taxes divided by Total Assets.
Return on Shareholder equity	Net income divided by Average Shareholders' Equity.
Earnings Per Share	Net Income after Taxes divided by Number of shares outstanding
Price Earnings Ratio	The ratio of a company's share price to the company's earnings per share

3.1 Econometric Specification of the Model

We have estimated the Covariates by using fixed effect modeling, before final estimations we execute some fundamental test to diagnose the precision and legitimacy of quantitative secondary information for the exploration study. Hausman test were run to choose between random and fixed effect model. First we compute the accounting profitability ratios from the yearly reports of firms. The future share price information were obtain form stock in the stock exchange. The covariates can be explained in the following model.

$$FSPi_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1ROAi_t + \beta_2ROEi_t + \beta_3EPSi_t + \beta_4PERi_t + \mu_i \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Here β_0 intercept and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 are coefficients.

FSPit+1, is the future share price while ROA, ROE, EPS and PER-(it) are the current year accounting profitability ratios, while μ it is the error term.

4.0 Results and Discussion

A skewness and kurtosis value for some of the variables has not fulfilling the assumption of normality. Hence according to the Gujarati (2009), Log of each variable has been taken to remove the issue of normality.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
FSP	209	-.1427	2.1493	.977893	.5428411
ROA	210	-1.1549	1.8603	.320843	.5622203
ROE	210	-.9586	2.8293	.562218	.7180722
EPS	210	-2.0000	1.3867	-.041590	.5799387
PER	210	-.3579	2.6109	.666618	.7139380

This table has identifying the maximum, minimum, mean and standard deviations of the predictors and outcome variable. Hence all the predictors of this study are normally distributed from their mean levels.

Table 3 Correlations Statistics

	FSP	ROA	ROE	EPS	PER
FSP	1				
ROA	.371**	1			
ROE	.180**	.678**	1		
EPS	.430**	.651**	.453**	1	
PER	.248**	.052	.006	-.466**	1

****Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

The ROA and ROE have positive 0.687, correlations each other at significance level 0.01. Financial market returns ratios EPS and PER have negative -.0466, correlation. Similarly the ROA and PER has positive correlation, while ROE and EPS positive correlation with each other. Hence it's indicating that all the variables of the study are different or not strongly correlated.

Table 4 Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	68.10	4	0.00

The test has a chi square of 68.1014 with p-value of 0.00, for future share price SP demonstrating chi-square values factually noteworthy and null hypothesis dismissed. Along these fixed effect model prescribed this study.

Table 5, Fixed Effect Model

Dependent Variable: Future Share Price (FSP)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.889651	0.041176	21.60628	0.0000
ROA	-0.017617	0.077872	-0.226230	0.8213
ROE	0.018468	0.051069	0.361627	0.7180
EPS	0.132835	0.103108	1.288307	0.1993
PER	0.132935	0.061024	2.178407	0.0306
R-squared	0.685081		F-statistic	16.67819
Adjusted R-squared	0.644004		Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000

The results of covariates shows that price earnings ratio has significant positive relationship with future share price and it is consistent with the finding of Fisher & Statman (2000), Kumar (2017) Subing *et al.*, (2017) but inconsistent with the study of (Auret & Sinclair, 2006). While return on shareholders' equity, return on assets, and earnings per-share insignificant to the future share price of investment firms and these findings supported by the study of (Laing & Dunbar, 2015) excluding EPS and inconsistent with the findings of (Subing *et al.*, 2017 and Hung, 2018). Hence it shows that the future share price of investment and securities firms in Pakistan can only be predicted with the help of current price earnings ratio in the market as market return ratio.

5.0 Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

This paper investigates the effect of accounting profitability ratios of listed firms on their future shares prices. We have used various components of profitability like return on assets, return on shareholders' equity, earnings per-share, and future share price. Financial ratios is a key attribute of valuable accounting information (FASB 2010), and accounting profitability ratios enables investors for better allocation of financial assets. We find that most of the accounting profitability ratios are insignificant with future share price except price earnings ratio. But we cannot completely isolate from the financial statement because it is the fundamental tenant of accounting theory. Profitability anomaly, arises when the expectations of investors for future profits too slowly and if the level of profits can be predicted by persistent publicly observable signals. Such observations could prove valuable to investors and managers. Managers can connect the accounting profitability information to the investors for future decision activities.

Simultaneously, speculators can break down accounting profitability ratios to get some important information for productive investment choices. The accounting profitability proportions convey experiences helpful for speculators since they face financial limitations. What's more, this examination explores whether these proportions predicts future stock returns and draws in an arrival premium? With the more prominent incorporation of monetary markets, the need to understanding the stock evaluating forms blended financial, social, social and political uncertainties that are related with how monetary policy to produce and share pertinent information in resource appraisal.

The true internal information has a strong effect on the future share price and too important in accounting and financial economics. Mitigating asymmetric information issues is the requirement of transparency and it has considered a major determinant of investment and financing. Internal accounting loss signals and asymmetric information between insiders and outsiders provide evidence of future potential value and financial growth. It supports the behavioral finance perspective on capital market peculiarities, which clarifies their reality as a marvel which can't be effectively arbitrated away. Future research may investigate extra financial statement ratios and accounting profitability ratios connected with future share price of the securities firms.

In some cases monetary or financial market information assumes a more do huge than bookkeeping or accounting information. Valuation models utilized market information for assessment than accounting information, at any rate over the present moment. Financial information has acquire in worth significance against accounting information after worldwide financial crisis for better assessments of stock returns and firm actual market values. Accounting information investigation objectives are, to the best utilization of accounting data for estimating, income, earnings management and valuation; and to check shortcomings of accounting data for predicting and valuation. Accounting information additionally utilized by speculators, investors, management of firms and standard setters can yield significant experiences for the utilization of budget accounting financial statements for forecasting and valuation.

5.1 Policy Recommendations

The goal of financial firms is to maximize the value of shareholders wealth, which ultimately translated into overall firm value. Investors demand summarize information to know the financial health of firms, based on their past and current performance they decide their favorable investments stocks. It means stock which offers steady and high returns compare to stocks having low return with same level of risks. Financial ratios are one of the tool used to evaluates overall firm performance, these includes firm ability to pay its obligations on time, dividends disbursements, and retaining some part of the earning for investments. The present study has significant policy implication for various shareholders interested to invest in financial firms listed on PSX.

Higher future stock prices must be possible with best utilization of financial assets by designing best connections between accounting profitability and future stock returns. High future stock returns can be obtained by increasing long run cheap financing mix. Agency problems and agency cost reduction can increased the future stock price of financial firms. Also diversified and flexible investment policy can open new horizon of earnings for financial firms in Pakistan.

The price earnings ratio significant positively affect the future share price of investment firms listed on Pakistan stock exchange, it means that increase in firm earning results in firm positive future returns. The investment sector of Pakistan remain in serious financial church in the last decade, government intervene with subsidized interest rates help the investment sector to remain financially healthy during this period. The finding suggests that investors earn sufficient returns on their investment to serve the interest of both stock and stakeholders.

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